

Tensile Behavior of Fiber/Particle Hybrid Metal Matrix Composites

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Abstract

This study presents a numerical model predicting the stress-strain curves of fiber reinforced (FMMCs) and fiber/particle reinforced metal matrix composites (F/P MMCs). The prediction is carried out by applying elastic theories up to the plastic deformation which is treated as an incrementally linear elastic behavior and by applying fiber-multi failure model to simulate the progressive fracture of reinforced fibers. Laminate theory based on the elastic constants of aligned short-fiber composite was used to evaluate the elastic modulus of FMMCs with 3D random fiber orientation distribution. The elastic constants of the aligned short fiber composites and of the particle reinforced composites (PMMCs) are predicted by Halpin-Tsai equation and numerical simulation. By combining the results of FMMCs and PMMCs using the rule of mixture, the prediction of F/P MMCs was performed. The predictions were compared with the test results for MMCs fabricated by squeeze casting method using Al_2O_3 short fiber and particle as reinforcement, and A356 aluminum alloy as matrix. Results show a good agreement of the stress-strain curves between the prediction and the experiments.

Key Words: short fiber, particle, stress-strain, MMC, tensile behavior

1. Introduction

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) are promising next-generation materials that are now in various areas of industry. Progress is being made in creating a low-cost, mass production system for commercialization. There are two aspects to this work; development of low-cost reinforcements and of low cost processing. Ceramic reinforcement is evolving from short fiber to particulate, which is superior for developing a new material because it is cheaper and because most ceramics can be produced in particulate form [1]. And as a low cost processing, squeeze casting is one of most widely used.

This study fabricated F/P MMCs with a low volume fraction of the total reinforcement (as low as 20%) by squeeze casting, taking economic advantage of both the squeeze casting process and the particulate reinforcement[2,3]. The F/P MMCs were made by the same processes as FMMCs for fabrication of the perform and the MMCs using relatively large size particle (diameter=45 μm) compared to the short-fiber (d=3 μm , L=150 μm). For the MMCs, tensile behavior was analyzed both by theory and experiment.

The tensile behavior of composites is divided into elastics and plastics. Elastic modulus is theoretically predictable because of a bulk property such as thermal expansion and the onset of plasticity.

The tensile strength is a point property affected by many local conditions. For the MMCs reinforced with ceramic short fiber or particle, it is difficult to predict the tensile strength because it is affected by many factors such as the end effects of reinforcement, interfacial condition between matrix and reinforcement, residual stress and reinforcement breakage, etc. Furthermore, the matrix takes on a more important role in MMCs compared to in polymer matrix composites. Therefore, most of the previous researches was limited to qualitative analysis on individual factors such as thermal treatments, reinforcement, effects of reinforcement type and effects of volume fraction.

Therefore, it is desirable to analyze the tensile strength of MMCs from the whole behavior of stress-strain rather than from theoretic prediction based on the strength of MMCs at the failure strain. This study predicted the stress-strain curves of MMCs using the elastic theory based on the assumption that 1) the major strengthening of MMCs results from the load transfer theory and 2) the failure mode is the failure of fiber reinforcements which is proved by many researchers [4,5]. This assumption also ignores the change of matrix properties and failure of particle reinforcements

2. Experiments

The composite materials studied made of Al₂O₃ (Saffil : ICI trade mark) short fiber, 3 μm in diameter and 150 μm in length, and Al₂O₃ particles about 45μm diameter as reinforcement and A356 aluminum as matrix. The mechanical properties of the reinforcement and the matrix are shown in Table 1.

The composition of the MMCs are listed in Table 2. The preforms were formed using 0.5 wt % inorganic (SiO₂) binder in the vacuum equipment and the MMCs were fabricated by squeeze casting method. The fabrication conditions are same as the previous research [6]. Fig.1 shows a SEM photograph of fiber/particle hybrid perform and optical micrograph of the MMCs' section. Both fibers and particles are uniformly distributed and broken fibers are not found indicating that fabrication of the hybrid perform was successful.

Tension test was performed using a Materials Test System (MTS 5ton) with displacement control 0.01mm/sec using ASTM standard tensile specimen.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of reinforcements

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Diameter (μm)	Length (μm)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio
Al ₂ O _{3f}	3.30	3	150	2,000	310	0.27
Al ₂ O _{3p}	3.85	45	-	-	380	-
A356	2.7	-	-	300	70	0.33

Table 2. Composition of the fabricated materials

Classification	Symbol	V _{total} (%)	V _f (%)	V _p (%)	Notice (F/P ratio)
Matrix	Al 356	-	-	-	
FMMCs	10	10	10	-	
	15	15	15	-	
	20	20	20	-	
F/P MMCs	F10P5	20	10	5	2:1
	F10P10	20	10	10	1:1
	F10P15	20	10	15	2:3

Fig. 1 (a) SEM photograph of Al_2O_3 F/P preform and (b) optical micrograph of the F/P MMCs; (F10P10; $V_f=V_p=10\%$)

3. Theory

The overall stress-strain behavior of the composites is numerically determined using the steps described in Table 3.

- Step 1. Elastic modulus for aligned FMMCs

The elastic modulus of short-fiber reinforced composites is strongly affected by the fiber orientation distribution (FOD). The elastic modulus of FMMCs with 3D random FOD is predicted by laminate theory using the elastic constants of aligned short-fiber composite. The properties of aligned short-fiber composites calculated by the Halpin-Tsai equation and numerical analysis. The longitudinal modulus E_{11} which depends on the fiber aspect ratios L/d is calculated from finite element analysis to consider fiber length change by fiber multi-failure.

Table 3. Numerical procedure used to calculate the elastic/plastic stress-strain curves of the FMFCs

The E_{11} is obtained by following equation using the stress-strain curve obtained by numerical analysis for the FEM model which is a axis symmetric representative volume element (RVE) as show in Fig. 2.

$$E_{11} = \frac{\Delta(\sigma_{c,RVE} |_{\varepsilon+\Delta\varepsilon} - \sigma_{c,RVE} |_{\varepsilon})}{\Delta\varepsilon_c} \quad (1)$$

As the composites strain increases by tensile loading, the stress acting on the fiber increases. When the stress reaches the failure stress, fiber breakage initiates at the middle parts of the fiber step by step until fiber length becomes smaller than the critical fiber length. Fig. 2 (a) shows the procedure of fiber failures from the aspect ratio ($s = L/d$) 40 to 20, 10 and 5. The E_{11} in Eq. (1) takes suitable stress-strain curve of the FEM model in Fig. 2(a) according to the composites strain and fiber orientation in FMFCs.

(a) (b)
 Fig. 2. FEM model of (a) aligned fiber reinforced composites, (b) particle reinforced composites.

Fig. 3. Predicted stress-strain curves of the aligned short-fiber composites with 10.% of fiber.

For example, a RVE of 30° orientation in FMMCs shown in Fig. 3 takes L/d=40 curve in calculating E_{11} in Eq.(1) until 1% tensile strain, takes L/d=20 and L/d=10 curve due to fiber failure between 1%~1.5% strain, and finally takes that of L/d=5.

• Step 2. Elastic modulus for randomly oriented FMMCs

The elastic modulus of FMMCs with 3D random FOD predicted using the laminate analogy theory [7]. The component of the stiffness matrix Q_{ij} that relates the stress to the strain for uniaxial ply for aligned FMMCs transformed to the off-axis system \bar{Q}_{ij} and the stiffness components of the fiber composites with 3D random fiber orientation are obtained by the following integration.

$$Q'_{ij} = \int_0^{\pi/2} \bar{Q}_{ij} \cdot \sin \theta d\theta \quad (2)$$

The elastic modulus of the fiber composites E_{cf} is then given by following equation.

$$E_{cf} = (Q'_{11}Q'_{22} - Q'^2_{12}) / Q'_{22} \quad (3)$$

• Step 3. Fiber/Particulate hybrid composites

The elastic modulus of F/P composite was predicted by the rule of mixture using the predictions of the single system E_{cf} and E_{cp} by following equation as explained in Fig. 4.

$$E_c = E_{cf} + E_{cp} - E_m \quad (4)$$

where E_{cf} and E_{cp} are the elastic modulus of fiber composite and particle composite with reinforcement volume fraction V_f and V_p , respectively.

Fig. 4. Concept of the rule of mixture for the prediction of elastic modulus of fiber/particle hybrid composites

4. Results and Discussion

Fig. 5 shows the representative stress-strain curves of FMMCs and F/P MMCs. The increase of reinforcement makes the MMCs brittle and as results the tensile strength increases and the failure strain decreases. The F/P MMCs is more brittle than FMMCs and the fiber found to be more efficient than particle on tensile strength and elongation. These results are compared with theoretical prediction as follows.

Fig. 6 shows the prediction and test results of FMMCs with 10 vol. % fiber. Prediction with fiber multi-failure shows better agreement with test result than without fiber failure as represented by dot line. The two prediction lines diverge about 0.7 % strain of composite where fiber failure begins.

Fig. 5. Representative stress-strain curves measured for each material

Fig. 6. Comparison of stress-strain curves of F10 MMCs measured and predicted

The number of fiber breakage represented by “#Fracture”. The breakage count is one for $L/d=40$ to $L/d=20$, and two for $L/d=20$ to $L/d=10$ and four for $L/d=10$ to $L/d=5$. The count is maximum about 0.7% strain and gradually reduced while the amount of void as shown in Fig.2 (a) increases linearly.

Fig. 7 represents the change of fiber length by fiber fracture as shown in Fig. 6. The fiber fraction of $L/d=40$ is 100% until about 0.7 % of tensile strain and gradually decreases by fracture. As the tensile strain increases, the fraction of $L/d=5$ increases because it is less than critical fiber length. The critical fiber length are calculated to be 9.75 according to the theory [8], by assuming the interfacial shear yield stress is $0.5 \sigma_{mu}$ and $\sigma_{mu} = 203\text{MPa}$ from test result of matrix shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 7. Variation of fiber length fraction by fiber multi-failure in F10 MMCs

Fig. 8 compares the stress-strain curves of FMMC between measured and predicted for FMMCs. As the fiber volume fraction increases, the difference between prediction and experiment become larger. The difference is considered to be a result of matrix endurance of fiber damage because the prediction derived on the assumption that matrix allows the fiber

damage infinitely. However, the matrix is also damaged by reinforcements breakage so that it contains void which lower the strength.

Fig. 9 shows the representative stress-strain curves of F/P MMCs. It shows that the addition of particle reinforcements increases the strength of the MMCs since the particle have positive effect on strengthening. The experiments are well matched with prediction performed by FEM result for the model shown in Fig. 2(b) and the rule of mixture.

Fig. 8. Comparison of stress-strain curves of FMCMCs measured and predicted

Fig. 9. Comparison of stress-strain curves of F/P MMCs measured and predicted

5. Conclusion

1. The tensile behavior of F/P MMCs and FMMCs can be predicted by applying the multi-failure model of fiber reinforcements; the reinforced fiber is gradually broken under tensile loading until it becomes shorter than the critical fiber length and the multi-failure determines the characteristic of plastic deformation of MMCs.
2. The multi-failure model works most effectively with MMC with a lower volume fraction fiber rather than higher because of the damage endurance of matrix; The tensile behavior of F/P MMCs can be more accurately predicted than FMMCs with the same volume fraction of reinforced because it contains a smaller amount of fibers

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